

Studies in Physico-Chemical Properties of Caseins. Part IV. Flocculation of Casein Sols by the Action of Electrolytes

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The action of Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions in flocculating casein sols at pH's 7 and 10.95 appears to involve the lowering of negative charge on the casein particles while that of the transition metal cations appears to be connected with chemical interaction involving complexing of the cations with the acid groups protonising at high pH values. The results at pH 7 indicate binding of imidazole groups by Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} cations. The results at pH 10.95 show binding of four acid groups by each of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} cations. The action of Ag^+ is much weaker and its flocculation value suggests binding of one acid group per Ag^+ ion. The power of these cations to bind acid groups follows the order $\text{Cu}^{2+} \approx \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Hg}^{2+} > \text{Ag}^+$. The action of di- and multivalent anions in flocculating casein sols, prepared at pH's 2.0 and 3.0, seems to involve only lowering of positive charge on the casein particles.

Casein, unlike other proteins, behaves as an intermediate colloid between emulsoids and suspensoids. This is due to the fact that casein particles are not so extensively hydrated. The stability of a casein sol, therefore, depends not merely on hydration but on electrification as well.

Casein sols can be prepared on either side of its isoelectric pH of 4.6. In acidic medium, i.e., at $\text{pH} < 4.6$, the stabilising charge is positive and this can be reduced on the addition of electrolytes with di- or multivalent anions. In alkaline medium, i.e., at pH values > 4.6 , the stabilising charge is negative and this can be reduced on the addition of electrolytes with di- or multivalent cations. The univalent anions or cations are too weak to produce any noticeable change within reasonable limits of concentration.

Most of the protein sols prepared in alkaline media are known to interact chemically, through their acidic groups capable of protonising at high pH values, with a number of transition metal cations. This phenomenon has been studied so far by equilibrium dialysis and potentiometric techniques. Since the resulting complexes are insoluble and incapable of dispersion under ordinary conditions, it appears that flocculation studies, being far simpler, may also be useful for such purposes.

The present work relates to the flocculation of casein sols, prepared at pH's 10.95 and 7.0 on the alkali side, and at pH's 2.0 and 3.0 on the acid sides of the isoelectric point, by the action of electrolytes containing effective cations in the first case and effective anions in the second case.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Casein samples were isolated from cows' milk by the rennet, ultra centrifuge, Hammersten, Zoller and Vanslyke-Bosworth methods as described before¹. Sols of 1% and 0.5% concentrations were prepared at *pH* 10.95 and of 1% only at *pH* 7.0 by suspending required amount of casein in 20 ml of CO₂-free distilled water in 100 ml. measuring flasks, adding enough of aqueous sodium hydroxide, gradually with constant stirring (magnetic), to dissolve the casein and to raise the *pH* value of the solution a little above 11 in one case and to 7.8 in the second case. The amounts of sodium hydroxide required for these purposes were obtained from the *pH*-titration curves of the caseins¹. The excess of the alkali was removed by dialysis. The *pH* values were checked at different stages and were finally adjusted at 10.95 (± 0.05) in one case and at 7.0 (± 0.05) in the other.

Casein sols of 1% concentration were also prepared at *pH* 2.0 and 3.0 (± 0.05). This was done by adding dilute hydrochloric acid to portions of casein sols prepared at *pH* 7, lowering the *pH* a little below the desired level and removing the excess of the acid by dialysis.

The electrolytes used for the sols in alkaline range were the chlorides of calcium, barium, nickel and mercury; sulphates of zinc and copper and nitrate of silver while those for the sols in acid range were the sulphate, arsenate and pyrophosphate of sodium, and dichromate, ferricyanide and ferrocyanide of potassium. All the chemicals used were of A.R. quality and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water.

Three ml. solutions of increasing concentrations of a given electrolyte were added to 2 ml. portions of a sol contained in a number of pyrex glass test tubes of equal bore and 20 ml. capacity. The tubes were inverted and re-inverted for five times and then allowed to stand in a thermostat maintained at 25° ($\pm 0.02^\circ$). The tubes were withdrawn after 10 min and checked if flocculation had occurred. Several sets of experiments for each sol electrolyte system had to be made in order to locate the minimum concentration needed to bring about flocculation under the experimental conditions.

R E S U L T S A N D D I S C U S S I O N

The flocculation values of different electrolytes, in terms of moles per mole (10⁵ g.)^a of casein, using 1% sol at *pH* 7, and 0.5 and 1% sol at *pH* 10.95, are given in Tables 1 and 2 respectively. The values for rennet and ultracentrifuge caseins could not be determined at *pH* 7 as it was not possible to dissolve them sufficiently to give sols of 1% or even 0.5% concentration at this *pH*.

The *pH* values of the coagula were found to be much above the isoelectric *pH* in every case. The values in the case of sols at *pH* 7 were found to vary between 6.1 and 6.8 while in the case of sols at *pH* 10.95 the values were found to be > 10 when calcium and barium salts were used, > 9 when salts of zinc, copper, nickel and silver were used and > 7 when mercuric chloride was used as flocculent.

It is seen that the flocculation values of the various electrolytes for the sols at *pH* 7 (Table 1) are appreciably lower than those for the sol at *pH* 10.95 (Table 2). This is, obviously, due to much lower charge and much smaller number of acid groups protonising at the lower *pH* values.

Considering the results for the sol at pH 7, in the first instance, it is seen that the flocculation values of Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} are much higher than those of the transition metal cations. This indicates that the action of these cations involves lowering of the zeta potential. The values of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions are sufficiently low to indicate complexing of these cations with some of the acid groups capable of protonising at this pH . Gurd and Goodman², in their work on interaction of albumin in the pH range 6-7.5 with zinc salts, employing equilibrium dialysis techniques, presented evidence to show that Zn^{2+} is bound principally to imidazole groups only. The intrinsic affinity constant of the complex also agreed with that for the simple zinc-imidazole complexes. There was no evidence for the participation of the carboxyl groups present in albumin. The results after blocking 12 of the carboxyl groups in human serum albumin³ also provided convincing proof that carboxyl groups interact only to a negligible extent with Zn^{2+} at this pH . The extremely low flocculation values of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} indicate that in caseins also it is the imidazole groups, ionising in the pH range 6.5-7, which alone are involved in the complexing process. The number of such groups in the various caseins have been shown¹ to vary between 20 and 25. It appears that Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} due to their much stronger tendencies can bind about 4 imidazole groups while Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} can bind only 2 and 1, respectively.

The behaviour of Ag^+ ion at this pH appears to be rather unusual, as has been observed by Ingram⁴ also in connection with his experiments on Horseoxyhemoglobin using equilibrium dialysis technique.

TABLE 1

Flocculation values (moles/10⁵ g. of casein) of different electrolytes for casein sols of 0.5 and 1% concentrations at pH 10.95

Electrolyte	Hammersten		Zoller		Vanslyke Bosworth		Rennet		Ultracentrifuge	
	1% sol	0.5% sol	1% sol	0.5% sol	1% sol	0.5% sol	1% sol	0.5% sol	1% sol	0.5% sol
Calcium chloride	710	790	800	890	995	1165	300	450	250	350
Barium chloride	715	790	750	835	950	1105	300	400	265	350
Copper sulphate	65	70	61	67	67	68	45	47	45	45
Nickel chloride	67	65	68	65	69	65	45	48	44	49
Zinc sulphate	73	75	73	75	77	80	54	56	46	50
Mercuric chloride	75	80	76	79	75	79	60	62	55	55
Silver nitrate	255	260	260	275	270	280	170	180	165	175
	(277)*		(286)*		(280)*					

+ The number of acid groups as obtained from the pH -titration curves (1).

Considering the results obtained with sols at pH 10.95 (Table 2), it is seen that the values of Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} , again, are of the same order and are considerably high, approaching, and in some cases even exceeding 1000 moles. This together with the fact that the flocculation values actually increase on dillution, as has been observed in the case of flocculation of milk as well^{5,6}, indicates that the action of these cations is confined very largely to the lowering of the charge and zeta potential of the system and there is little or no chemical interaction involved in the process. Northrop and Kunitz⁷ in their equilibrium dialysis

studies with gelatin sols at high *pH* values also found little evidence for any chemical binding of the alkaline earth ions.

TABLE 2

Flocculation values (moles/10⁵ g. of casein) of different electrolytes for casein sols of 1% concentration at pH 7.0

Electrolyte	Hammarsten	Zoller	Vanslyke-Bosworth
Calcium chloride	110	119	144
Barium chloride	102	109	123
Copper sulphate	5.1	5.4	5.9
Nickel chloride	5.8	6.0	6.1
Zinc sulphate	12.1	12.0	12.3
Mercuric chloride	25	25	30
Silver nitrate	63	64	68

The flocculation values of Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions for the Vanslyke-Bosworth casein are seen to be the highest while those for the rennet and ultra centrifuge caseins are amongst the lowest. This appears to be due to the fact that while the former was almost completely freed of calcium in the course of its preparation, the latter varieties were isolated at *pH* 6.6 at which most of the ionisable acid groups, such as carboxyl and phosphatic, remain bound to calcium and magnesium in the caseinate complex.

The flocculation values of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Hg^{2+} and Ag^+ ions are seen to be very much lower than those of Ca^{2+} and Ba^{2+} ions and are seen to be almost independent of the concentration of the sol. This suggests occurrence of chemical interaction of quantitative nature between these cations and the caseinate anions produced by the protonisation of the various acid groups in casein at the prevailing high *pH* value of 10.95.

The flocculating powers of the various cations are seen to decrease in the order

It may be noted that the capacity of some of these cations to bind and complex simple amino acids and peptides, such as glycine, alanine and glycyl glycine, at high *pH* values has been found⁸ to follow almost the same decreasing order as reported above. It appears highly likely, therefore, that the flocculating action of these cations on the various casein sols at *pH* 10.95 is very largely, if not entirely, due to their capacity to complex the various ionic acid groups in casein.

It is seen further that the flocculation values of a given transition metal cation for the three acid caseins i.e., Hammarsten, Zoller and Vanslyke-Bosworth caseins, are fairly close to one another. The values for the rennet and ultra centrifuge caseins which, as mentioned earlier, had their carboxyl and phosphatic groups already bound, are much lower, as expected.

Klotz, Fallner and Urquhart⁹ have adduced spectroscopic evidence to show that in the copper- β -lactoglobulin complex formed at *pH*'s ≥ 9.8 , which are sufficiently high for the protonization of NH_3^+ groups also, the Cu^{2+} ion is tetraordinated, two bonds being directed towards the carboxyl and the other two towards the amino groups. Casein contains a small proportion of free phosphoric acid groups as well and since these groups also ionise in the

same pH range as carboxyl groups¹, it seems reasonable to assume that Cu^{2+} ion can bind these groups also in the same way. Further, since about half of the acid groups in casein are carboxylic and phosphoric while the other half are the amino and other similar groups¹, each Cu^{2+} ion may be considered in general to bind 4 of the acid groups present in casein. It is interesting to note that the flocculation value of Cu^{2+} ion for each of the acid caseins corresponds roughly to one fourth of the total number of acid groups. The number of these acid groups, as obtained from the pH titration curves of the casein as reported earlier¹, are reproduced at the bottom of the table in parentheses. The flocculation values of Ni^{2+} ions are also seen to be about the same as those of Cu^{2+} ions. It appears that the complexing of Ni^{2+} ions with casein at high pH values is similar to that of Cu^{2+} ions.

The flocculation values of Zn^{2+} and Hg^{2+} ions, although in fair agreement with each other, are seen to be slightly higher than those of Cu^{2+} and Ni^{2+} ions. This appears to be due to their relatively weaker tendency to form complexes with protein anions⁸ as a result of which a slightly higher concentration should be needed for the chemical interaction involved.

The flocculation values of Ag^+ ions are seen to be much higher. The perusal of the literature shows that Ag^+ has a much weaker complexing tendency with simple amino acids and peptides⁹ or with proteins like oxyhemoglobins¹⁰. Our results based on measurement of flocculation values of Ag^+ show the same trend with casein. The number of Ag^+ ions required for flocculation, however, is seen to be very close to the total number of acid groups, indicating as if one Ag^+ ion can bind one acid group. It is not possible to say how far this agreement is significant or fortuitous unless similar work is extended to several other proteins as well.

The flocculation values of the various transition metal cations for the rennet and ultra-centrifuge caseins are appreciably lower as expected for the reasons already mentioned.

The flocculation values of some of the electrolytes with different effective anions for casein sols at pH 2.0 and 3.0 are recorded in Table 3. The values are appreciably higher for the sols at pH 2.0 than those for the sols at pH 3.0. This effect, obviously, is due to greater electrification of the particles at the lower pH values. The effect of anionic valency is seen to be appreciable, although it is not so dominant as observed generally in lyophobic systems. Nevertheless, it appears highly likely that the flocculation of the sols in the

TABLE 3

Flocculation values (m.moles/lit.) of different electrolytes for casein sols of 1% concentration at pH's 2.0 and 3.0

Electrolyte	Effective anion valency	Hammarsten sol at		Zoller sol at		Vanslyke Bosworth sol at		Rennet sol at	
		pH 2.0	pH 3.0	pH 2.0	pH 3.0	pH 2.0	pH 3.0	pH 3.0	pH 3.0
Sodium sulphate	2	30.10	9.85	28.40	12.00	28.00	14.00	30.00	20.00
Sodium arsenate Na_2HAsO_4	2	3.60	1.45	3.40	1.40	3.45	1.40	3.67	3.10
Potassium dichromate	2	3.00	1.20	2.21	1.00	2.21	1.00	3.05	2.21
Sodium pyrophosphate	2	2.00	0.70	1.91	0.65	1.90	0.65	2.05	1.40
Sodium ferricyanide	3	0.50	0.20	0.60	0.20	0.56	0.20	0.55	0.48
Sodium ferrocyanide	4	0.42	0.18	0.41	0.18	0.41	0.18	0.48	0.40

present case takes place largely through the lowering of the zeta potential. The flocculation values of SO_4^{2-} are unusually high. This may perhaps be due to the relatively smaller size and, therefore, lower adsorbability of this ion at the interface.

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